
Effect of Personality and Birth order on Job stress of Bank Employees

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Introduction:

The term “Stress” is derived from the Latin word ‘stranger’ later this was used in 15 century as shortand of apathetic from the distress (Rees 1976) to denote obnoxious human experience. The oxford English dictionary informs that in 17th century “stress” means “hardship” strait, advertising however the 18th century and 19 century the term was differently used pressure, strain or strong efforts excited or upon a material objects or person upon a person’s organs. we are living in the era of growing complexities and pressure where human constitution and capacities are being taxed severely. The stress relating to the job have become predominate future of modern life. Excreting for reaching effects on local employee’s behavior and adjustment on as well as of the job. Job stress generally defined in times of relationship between person and environment. Margolis and Kroes (1974) Job stress as a condition worth interacting with worker characteristics to disrupt psychological homeostasis.

The caused situations, conditions are job stress is as and the disrupted home stasis is job rotated strain:

According to Cridla Geothals, Kavonaugh and Soloman (2001) “Stress is a patterns of disrupted psychological and Physiological functioning that occurs when as environmental event appraised a threat to important goals and one’s ability to cope”

According to J.D Brod Zinski, RF Saberer and K.A Goyar (1999)

“Stress is the interaction between the individual and environment characterized by physiological and psychological changes that cause a deviation from normal performance”.

“Stress may be defined in many different ways from Physiological point of view, stress may be defined as any state during which body tends to mobilize its resources and utilize more energy than the ordinate word” Loyle E, Boome, and Brucy Ecotrand (2002)

The Psychologist and management scientists have different views on job stress. The researches engaged in analyzing the antecedents consequents of Job stress have reported different physical and Psychological conditions at work as potential occupational stressors.

PERSONALITY

Personality is one of the most interesting but at the same time very difficulties to conceptualize. Psychologist definition of Personality considerably differs from that of layman. Personality has recently become the prime topic of academic Interest and has reached its acme during the few decades. The work personality has been derived from latin word 'persona' Which was used for the "Mask utilize by the actors to change their but in roman times it was taken as a particular character it safe since then the work personality is used to refer not only to ones character but also to those aspects of individuals behavior that set him apart from but other individuals. It is not easy to define personality some psychologist definition presents him.

Characteristics of type - A personality:

- Restless - Always moves, walks and eats rapidly.
- Impatient - dislike waiting.
- Does more than one thing at time.
- Try to schedule more and more in less and less time
- Does not complete one thing before starting the other.
- Does not have time to relax and enjoy of life.

Characteristics of type -B personality:

Type 'B', Personality character are opposite to the one that are stated type B behavior Persons are hard working detailed oriented people with high performance standards. These people have difficulty in creating interpersonal relationship and create a lot of for themselves and the people they type "B" Person Put in extra efforts order to meet a dead time don't feel Pressurized.

BIRTH ORDER :

Birth order refers to the order of birth of the individual in relation to his siblings. This is also known as the ordinal position of the person in his family. In psychological researches birth order has been considered an important independent variable and it has a marked influence on the personality of

the individual. for example, as uncertain, mistrustful, shrewd, stingily and wealthy. These characteristics show a personality patterns which leads to poor personal and social adjustment. By contrast, the last born has the favored position. He is secure, over, confidence, generous, good natured, human and generally well adjusted. It was Sigmund Freud who first studied the relationship between ordinal position and the individual scientifically. He claimed that the person's position in the sequence of brothers and sisters, is very great significance for the choose of his later life. Adler (1930) emphasized that each position provides a predictable personality pattern, with that of the middle and last child more favorable than that of the first born. Likely, Rank (1929) emphasized that the last born has a more favorable position as far as personality is concerned, than the first born.

Recent studies show that "psychological position" of the person in the family is more important in the shaping and molding of his personality than his ordinal position. Chittenden (1968) observed that the first born is "brought up" while the others "grow up". Some other studies reveal that later born have siblings to identify with are thus freed from some of the pressures and exceptions that come with almost exclusive adult identification (Greenburg 1963; MC Arther 1956, Warren, 1966). Singer J.E. and P.F. Lamb, (1966) found that the first born are usually more affected by their body builds than later born. The greater anxiety and concerned first born have about their body builds has been explained as part of the "first born syndromes" of insecurity and dependency. Shrader W.K. and T. Leventhal (1968) studied that children are unable to confirm to parental expectation, they often become anxious, resentful and reliable. This frequently leads to behaviour problems. The behaviour ratings for children of different ordinal position show that the first born present more problems for their parents than those born later. Holeson, R (1968) Munz, D.C. (1968) D. Smoos & G Letlworth, Schachter. (1963) studies have repeatedly pointed out that the typical first born enjoys a number of advantages. These advantages are largely responsible for the personality that is so characteristically found among first born on the whole, achievement is greater among first, than among later borns in the same family (102) (104) (193).-

Bossard J.H. (1966) Handerson, G.E. (1969) Sears, R.R., E.E. Maccabo (1957) found that the baby of the family is likely to be pampered and spoiled by siblings as well as parents, and little is expected of him.

Both become self centered, selfish, and bossy, but for different reasons. (27, 103, 199)

PROBLEM

In the present study the effect of personality and Birth order on Job stress of Bank employees.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference in job stress of Bank employees. exhibiting type 'A' personality patterns and Type 'B' personality patters of the Bank employees.
2. There is no significant difference in job stress of bank employees. who are first born and the last born the first born and the last born Bank employees will show the same amount of job stress.

METHOD

A factorial design of 2×2 with 4 independent cells consisting two levels of personality type 'A' personality and Type 'B' personality and two level of Birth order First Born and last Born.

SAMPLE

Thus the total sample of 240 subject 120 type a personating and 120 Type B personality and 60 Ss of first born and 60 Ss Last Born of first Born and 60 Last Born in this research the following test were used for Data Collection.

(A) Type A and Type B Personality Patterns Scale : Type A and Type B

Behavior patterns scale (Upeindhar Dhar was uses to measure the Job stress of the subject.)

RESEARCH TOOL

(OSI) occupational stress index A Hindi version job stress scale developed by Dr. A.K Srivastava and Dr. A.P. Singh (1981) was used to measure the job stress of the subjects.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DATA

In order to find out the significant effects of the two independent variable on the dependent variable i.e, Job stress. The data were analyzed using two way analysis of variable technique.

The effects of independent variable type of personality on job stress in significant at 01 level of confident ($F= 1, 216 = 9.446 > .01$) this indicates that type of personality is an important factor influencing the levels of job stress. These the null hypotheses is rejected and the substantive hypotheses that there is a significant difference in job stress of two levels personality is accepted.

Table -1 Means Job stress scores as a function of personality (Pt)

Type of personality	Total	N	Mean Score
Pt _A	16325	120	136.042
Pt _B	16683	120	139.025
Total	33008	240	137.533

Mean scores in terms of Job stress of two group type A personality and type B personality

Table-1 shows the mean type of personality- The mean of Pt_B (M= 139.025) is greater than of type personality (Pt_A) (M= 136.042) subjects. It can be calculates that the subject of Pt_B personality have more job stress.

Fig-1 Means Job stress scores as a function of personality (Pt)

The F ratio for the second factor i.e Birth order which is not significant at .05 level of confidence (F= 1,216= 0.382 < .05). This shows that Birth order is not a potential factor influencing the Job stress. Thus the will Hypotheses is retained and substantive was not accepted that there is significant difference in job stress of subjects first Born and last Born.

Table-2 Mean Scores in terms of job stress for Two level of Birth order

Level of Birth order	Total	N.	Mean Scores
Br _F	16540	120	137.833
Br _L	16468	120	137.233
Total	33008	240	137.533

Fig-2 Means job stress scores as a function of Birth Order.

Table 2 Shows that subjects who are first born have mean Job scores 137.833 and who are last born have mean scores on job stress 137.233 in other word. we can say that the mean scores of two groups are approximately same. even figure-2 reveals that the bar of the graph of two groups is almost the parallel.

INTERACTION EFFECT:

Effects of personality and Birth order the two way interaction between personality and Birth order is not significant at .01 levels of confidence ($F=1, 216=2.441 < .01$) on the basis obtained results. it may be concluded that these is no significant difference between job stress of different groups of personality and birth order of different level.

It might be interpreted that both the factor i.e personality and Birth order are independent of each other and don't interact with each other in any significant way for this comparison means scores of two levels of personality with two combination of Birth order were calculated which were shows in Table-3.

Table-3 Mean Job Stress in scores as a function of personality and Birth order

Birth Order	Levels of Personality	
	Pt _A	Pt _B
Br _F	135.583	136.500
Br _L	140.083	137.966

Fig-3 Mean Job Stress in scores as a function of personality and Birth order

The mean scores of table 3 are graphically presents in figure-3 in which birth order, type of personality are plotted along the abscissa and mean of job stress score on the ordinate. The Bar diagram shows that bar are likely similar.

CONCLUSION

1. Types of personality is a significant factor to determine the Job stress level of the individual and the amount of Job stress is higher in type B personality individuals to type A personality individual.

2. Birth order is not a significant determinate of job stress of the individual and the magnitudes of job stress in first born individuals and the last Born individuals are statistically equal.
3. The interaction of types of personality and Birth order is not a significant factor determining the Job Stress level of Individual.

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